
Lifestyle Education for 9th Grade Students through the Lesson: Ho Chi Minh Style

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ABSTRACT: Students, especially middle school students, are showing more and more deviations in their lifestyle, not conforming to social standards, and gradually losing the nation's cultural identity. "Ho Chi Minh's style" is an essay in the 9th Literature program, pointing out the noble and simple beauty of Ho Chi Minh, from which to educate students in the lifestyle and ways of doing things. Work, conduct, etc. in accordance with the moral standards of society, and preserve the cultural identity of the nation.

KEY WORD: Lifestyle, 9th grade students, Ho Chi Minh style, Literature.

1. Ask a problem

Lifestyle is the way of living, working, behaving, etc. that creates the uniqueness of a person or a certain class of people. It is a culture and is characterized by a view of reality, personality, personal identity, as well as influenced by the surrounding environment such as family, place of living, education, culture and media.

Each individual, with different personalities and social awareness, will have different lifestyles. That's individuality. But in a society, individuals' private lifestyles must follow the general regulations of society, which are social norms.

Social norms are cultural features typical of a society or a nation, accepted by the majority of people in that society. It is the standard for evaluating each individual in society, and a guideline for the development of society.

Currently, with the "open door" mechanism of the State, creating conditions for foreign investment in Vietnam, causing the economy to develop rapidly, the material life of the people is increasingly improved and enhanced. . At the same time, it is an opportunity for the introduction of many different cultures, causing many changes in people's lifestyles, especially students.

Students, especially middle school students, are the age that psychology calls the "crazy" age. They are no longer children, but they are not yet adults, and their social awareness is still immature. When exposed to different cultures, they are not aware of what is right, good, and standard compared to Vietnamese society, thus affecting their lifestyle. Many children have led lifestyles that deviate from social standards , gradually losing the nation's cultural identity, expressed in dress, speech, behavior towards teachers and friends,...

With these deviations of students, families and schools must be the places to directly educate them so that they understand right and wrong, thereby bringing them back to social standards. cultural features of the nation.

In school, with different subjects and different characteristics, they will take on different roles in educating children's personalities. Literature is a subject that equips students with views on truth, goodness and beauty. Therefore, it is a very convenient subject in educating students' character.

2. Some details about the article "Ho Chi Minh's Style"

The article "Ho Chi Minh's Style" is the first text lesson in the lesson set of Grade 9 Literature. This is an article by author Le Anh Tra, excerpted from "Ho Chi Minh's Style, the greatness associated with with simplicity", of Ho Chi Minh and Vietnamese culture, Institute of Culture publishing house, Hanoi, 1990.

"Ho Chi Minh style" is a type of argumentative text, with diverse modes of expression: exposition, description, narrative, discussion and expression. These methods of expression are used interwoven in paragraphs, creating a text with a strict, logical and coherent argument system. There is a natural continuity between these arguments and they complement and explain each other, with authentic, convincing evidence. Using formal language to express Ho Chi Minh's style is a harmonious combination of nationalism and humanity, tradition and modernity, greatness and simplicity.

The excerpt "Ho Chi Minh's Style" is structured into 3 paragraphs:

Part 1 is the process of forming Ho Chi Minh's cultural style.

Part 2 is about the specific beauty of Bac's living and working style.

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Paragraph 3 is comments and affirms the meaning of Ho Chi Minh's cultural style.

The paragraphs connected together to build the content of the entire article are: Ho Chi Minh's culture is the crystallization of profound understanding of the world's peoples and cultures. Although knowledgeable and influenced by the cultures of many countries and regions around the world, Ho Chi Minh's style is extremely simple. That is shown right in his daily life. The place to live is just a small stilt house with rustic furniture, simple clothes, frugal food... However, the most wonderful thing about Uncle Ho is the harmonious combination of national cultural traditions and The quintessence of humanity, between nobility and simplicity .

Uncle Ho's simple and frugal lifestyle is not at all a way to deify himself, to make himself different, better than the world, but this is a noble lifestyle, a way of spiritual nourishment, an aesthetic concept. about life, capable of bringing noble happiness to the soul and body.

The essay "Ho Chi Minh's Style" helps readers understand more deeply about his style - a great leader of the Vietnamese people, a cultural celebrity of the world.

The lesson wants to educate students in simple virtues, which is noble beauty, a social standard that we must aim for. The lesson also raises issues in the integration period: absorbing the cultural quintessence of humanity, while at the same time knowing how to preserve and promote national cultural identity.

3. Lifestyle education for 9th grade students through the lesson "Ho Chi Minh Style"

3.1. Comprehensive viewpoint

Lifestyle education for 9th grade students through the lesson "Ho Chi Minh's Style" is just an integrated content. The main content of the lesson is still aimed at helping students understand the text and know how to use some artistic measures in explanatory text. Because it is an integrated content, the amount of time for this content is not much, but there needs to be in-depth elements to "hit hard" on students' ideology and ethics, in order to change their thinking and behavior. their movements.

3.2. Lifestyle education for 9th grade students through the lesson "Ho Chi Minh Style"

Like other texts, teachers let students learn in general about the text: origin, text style,... then learn about the text.

To learn the text, the teacher has one or two students read the text aloud in front of the class, while the other students follow the text in their textbooks. At the end of the text reading, the teacher asks students questions to understand the text such as: How many paragraphs does the text have? From where to where?, what is the content of each paragraph?... then the teacher explains each paragraph.

Paragraph 1: From "In a life full of hardships..." to "...very modern". This is a paragraph about the process of forming Ho Chi Minh's cultural style.

To teach this section, teachers can give a system of small questions to show students how extensive Ho Chi Minh's human cultural knowledge is. Questions like:

Which continents and countries have you visited?

- What languages do you speak and write fluently?

- How many jobs have you done?

After students answer these questions, the teacher will emphasize and inculcate: Ho Chi Minh's human cultural knowledge is very extensive. He has traveled to many places and encountered many cultures from the East to the West. He has a deep understanding of the cultures of Asian, European, African, American countries... Few leaders know as much about the world's nations and people as deeply as Uncle Ho. People speak and write fluently in many foreign languages such as English, French, Chinese, Russian, etc. It is the most important communication tool to learn and interact with peoples around the world.

When it comes to this passage, in order for students to admire the leader's profound learning, teachers can ask questions for students to ponder: you learn a foreign language, that is English, you are good at learning. How to speak and write?

The teacher then continued to lecture: That cultural and intellectual capital was obtained because during his arduous journey to find a way to save the country, he came into contact with the cultures of many countries. He also worked in many professions to gain in-depth knowledge in many fields, and through that he also learned... Wherever he went, he learned and learned about the culture and art of that country.

The teacher asks the question: What can we learn from him?. Students answer according to their thinking. Then the teacher educates the students' ethics: We are young people, we have the conditions to study, we need to strive to study well, not afraid of difficulties to strive for a bright future, ...

When interacting with cultures, he is always conscious of absorbing the beauty and goodness, while also criticizing the negative.

In his position as a leader, head of a state, he was exposed to many different cultures, but his national cultural roots were unshakable. He still lived a very simple lifestyle. Very Vietnamese, but also very new and modern. Look for signs of Uncle Ho's simple lifestyle in paragraph 2?.

Paragraph 2: From "For the first time in history..." to "bathing in the pond". This is a paragraph about the specific beauty of Uncle Ho's living and working style.

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After the students mentioned the manifestations of Ho Chi Minh's simple lifestyle, the teacher emphasized and engraved this content: In the highest leadership position of the country, Uncle Ho had an extremely simple and very simple lifestyle. Vietnam, very Oriental, is shown through many details in daily life:

- Uncle Ho's residence and workplace are very simple: a wooden house on stilts next to a pond. That stilt house only had a few rooms for receiving guests, meeting with the Politburo, working and sleeping, with very rustic and simple furniture.
- Very simple outfit: brown three-piece outfit, guard shirt, rudimentary tire sandals; meager personal belongings: a small suitcase with a few clothes, a few souvenirs,...
- Eat frugally: braised fish, boiled vegetables, pickled vegetables, pickled eggplant, flower porridge,...

In the excerpt, the author used the art of expression through comparison and contrast to clarify the beauty of Ho Chi Minh's lifestyle: "For the first time in the history of Vietnam and perhaps the whole world, There was a President who took a wooden house on stilts next to a pond as his "palace". It's like a myth, like the story of a fairy, some supernatural person in a fairy tale."

This is the first phenomenon we have seen, a country's highest leader has enough conditions to build for himself a magnificent castle, a magnificent palace... like many other leaders. live and work, but Uncle Ho only chose a simple house to live and work. Truly an "abnormal" person in real society. The author compares this "unusual" person to a fairy, some supernatural person that only exists in fairy tales and myths. A "normal" person is often tempted by material things, often wants to eat and wear well,... but why does Uncle Ho do that? He chose this simple lifestyle because he always thought about the people: our people were still hungry, had no food, no warm clothes, etc., so he could not ask for anything for himself. Always thinking of others, sharing difficulties with everyone is Uncle Ho's cultural behavior, which is also a beauty in Vietnamese customs and traditions.

Uncle Ho's clothes and meals were also very simple: brown three-piece suit, guard shirt, tire sandals; braised fish, boiled vegetables, pickled vegetables, pickled eggplants... Uncle has enough strength to have luxurious suits and eat happily, but why is he so simple? Because Uncle came from a farmer, he understood the poverty that farmers had to endure. He did not want to separate himself from the common situation, he wanted to share! A great man! A person who always blends in with the common situation and knows how to share difficulties with others.

At the end of this paragraph, the author once again uses the art of comparison to highlight Ho Chi Minh's simple style, which is a comparison with the sages Nguyen Trai or Nguyen Binh Khiem, who are talented people. , virtuous, profound knowledge, honored by people. The author quoted two verses in the poem Nhan by Nguyen Binh Khiem, both to compare Ho Chi Minh's lifestyle to that of the sage Nguyen Binh Khiem, and to connect to paragraph 3 to comment and confirm the meaning. of Ho Chi Minh cultural style:

*"In autumn we eat bamboo shoots, in winter we eat bean sprouts
In the spring, bathe in the lotus pond, in the summer, bathe in the pond.*

This is a spiritual life and lifestyle close to the ecological environment, natural conditions and natural scenery; a leisurely lifestyle, promoting noble spiritual enjoyment, a way of spiritual nourishment, an aesthetic concept of life, capable of bringing noble happiness to the soul and body.

When teaching this paragraph, the teacher may ask: "Why can it be said that your lifestyle is a combination of simplicity and elegance?" for students to comment. The teacher can then comment: Ho Chi Minh's simple and frugal lifestyle is an expression of the beauty of his very noble soul. This is not the austere lifestyle of people who are happy in poverty, nor is it a way to deify themselves, to make themselves different from others, superior to others. This is a cultural way of life that has become an aesthetic concept: beauty is simplicity and nature. However, it is simple but not sketchy, frugal but does not evoke a feeling of destitution, from the decoration to the accommodation and daily activities all show serenity and leisure. That life seems close to the life of a sage or a fairy, but it is not quite like that. That is the bravery and will of a great revolutionary soldier merged with the soul of a great poet and a great culturer. The more he yearned to contribute to the Fatherland and the people, the more he loved nature and life. The beauty of the external elements, from the house, garden, fish pond to costumes, eating, speaking,... all clearly show the beauty of his soul, very strong but also very romantic. , poetic.

After completing the review and also ending paragraph 3, the teacher asks questions to educate students' personality: What do you feel and learn from "Ho Chi Minh's Style"?

The teacher can call on 2 or 3 students to express their feelings and lessons, then ask the question: Please state the manifestations of the student's current style?. This question has a very high moral educational effect, because after students point out the manifestations of today's student lifestyle, they will have to compare it with Ho Chi Minh's lifestyle to learn. and self-adjust and mold themselves to conform to social standards.

In terms of teaching methods, in the above question, teachers should use the brainstorming method, not commenting on students' answers, but letting them list the popular lifestyles of students today, as many as possible. the better. Then the teacher offers another system of questions for the students to ponder and draw lessons for themselves, such as: Ho Chi Minh is a leader who has made great contributions to the country. , for the nation, yet He asked nothing for himself. So what about you? What have you done for your family and society? And what have you asked for from your parents and society? Do you know how to sympathize and share difficulties? with others?...

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Then the teacher emphasized: Spiritual beauty is eternal beauty and is honored by the whole society. Each of us needs to nurture, study and practice according to Ho Chi Minh's moral example.

4. CONCLUSION

The article "Ho Chi Minh's Style" is an argumentative essay in the Grade 9 Literature program that has a very high effect of integrating moral education.

Current social reality has caused students to have many deviations in ethics and lifestyle, inconsistent with the nation's fine customs and traditions, and depart from social moral standards, which is a very dangerous thing. . Through President Ho Chi Minh's simple but very noble, very traditional but very modern style, teachers can evoke human lessons for students, questions that make students reconsider themselves. to shape themselves to match the cultural beauty of the nation.

This article by the author is only intended to suggest a certain part of the lesson "Ho Chi Minh's Style" for 9th grade students, in order to make a small contribution to the moral education of students.

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